

Implementation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Filipino Instruction at a Grade Level: An Assessment

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the status of implementation in teaching of Department of Education (DepEd) Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Filipino 10 by the teachers in secondary schools in Surigao City, Philippines. The researcher employed a quantitative-descriptive research design utilizing survey technique. A modified questionnaire was administered to various secondary schools in Surigao City, except for St. Paul University Surigao, where Google Forms were used. The participants of this study were the teachers who teach Filipino 10 in the secondary schools of Surigao City. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution and Chi-Square Test were used for data analysis and interpretation. The results of the research revealed that in the implementation of Most Essential Learning Competencies in Filipino 10, most of the teachers answered that it has been taught, which means that the competencies are generally implemented in the secondary schools of Surigao City. Additionally, the study found that there was no significant relationship between the variables. However, the highest educational attainment by the teachers is related to teaching listening skills. The researcher recommends that the teachers in the secondary schools of Surigao City may continue the implementation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in Filipino 10 by the Department of Education.

Keywords: *Assessment, Learning Competencies, Secondary Teachers, Modified Questionnaire, Listening.*

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Introduction

The current global health crisis has profoundly impacted the education system, with approximately 87% of the global student population, or nearly 1.5 billion learners, affected by school closures (UNESCO, 2020). In response to the ongoing situation, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) to be used by schools in teaching through various distance learning modalities (Gaddi et al., 2024; Dacoylo et al., 2024). This is also in line with the DepEd Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan implemented in schools to ensure the continuation of teaching and learning despite the pandemic.

The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) are defined as the skills that a student needs to progress to the next grade levels and, ultimately, lead a successful life (DepEd, 2020). These competencies were identified by DepEd's Curriculum and Instruction Bureau through the Bureau of Curriculum Development. According to a report from the Manila Times (Azizah et al., 2017), Undersecretary Nepomuceno Malaluan stated that the K-12 curriculum was streamlined, reducing

the MELCs from 14,171 to 5,689, a 60% reduction. This helps the department focus on teaching the most critical and necessary skills that students must acquire, while anticipating the challenges in learning (Gaddi et al., 2024; Eliot et al., 2024).

The pandemic has brought about changes in the delivery of education in the country, transitioning from physical classrooms to modular, online, and other learning modalities. According to the study by Onyema et al. (2020), the pandemic has negatively impacted students' academic interest and performance. It has also affected the quality of teaching, learning, and academic success, especially for students who are struggling with their studies. Although technology is being used as a remedy, it cannot fully replace the vital impact of face-to-face interaction between teachers and students (Languing et al., 2023). These are the changes brought by this crisis, where all students are adapting to the new norm of teaching and learning. Due to these challenges, teachers face obstacles in implementing DepEd's MELCs in their teaching (Gaddi, 2024; Platil et al., 2024).

In Winthrop's (2020) study, it is stated that other issues being faced today include a lack of equity, safety, and security for students. The quality of learning has been compromised, and assessment results are poor. The new normal in education has brought about teaching and learning issues that have affected teachers. These problems motivated the researcher to conduct this study on the status of the implementation of DepEd's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Filipino 10, based on the assessment of teachers in secondary schools in Surigao City, Philippines.

The study aims to assess the status of the implementation of DepEd's MELCs in teaching Filipino 10. This study focuses on the learning competencies in Filipino 10, as these are crucial for students entering Senior High School and should, therefore, be taught by teachers. The results of this study will serve as the basis for proposing recommendations.

Methods

This is a quantitative approach that utilized a descriptive research method, specifically employing a survey technique. The respondents of the study were teachers who taught Filipino 10 in secondary schools in Surigao City during the 2020-2021 school year. There were twenty-one (21) respondents in this study. The researcher selected the population from each school since the number of teachers teaching Filipino 10 was limited. The researcher used a validated modified questionnaire based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Filipino 10 to collect the data, consisting of two parts. The first part focused on the respondents' profile in terms of the highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, number of students taught in Grade 10, type of school, and teaching modality used. The second part addressed the status of the implementation of DepEd's MELCs in teaching Filipino 10. The statistical tools used in the research were Frequency Count, Percentage Distribution, and the Chi-Square Test.

Results and Discussion

This section shows the major findings of the study.

Respondents' Profile

Figure 1 illustrates the profile of the 21 teachers who taught Filipino 10 in secondary schools across Surigao City. The majority of the respondents came from public schools, making up 76.19% of the population, and predominantly used modular-print learning methods (61.90%). This reliance on modular learning aligns with DepEd's strategies during the pandemic, as many students lacked access to digital tools for online learning (DepEd, 2020). Most of the teachers held a baccalaureate degree (66.67%) and had between six and ten years of teaching experience (42.86%), teaching class

sizes ranging from 1 to 50 students (33.33%). This profile provides a glimpse into the teaching landscape during a time when educators were adapting to new modalities and addressing learning gaps caused by the pandemic.

Figure 1. Profile of the Respondents

Status of Implementation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Teaching Filipino 10 among Secondary Teachers

Figure 2. Implementation Status of MELCs in Teaching Filipino 10 in terms of Listening, Reading, Speaking, and Writing

Figure 2 shows the implementation status of MELCs in teaching Filipino 10 in terms of listening, reading, speaking, and writing. The data reveal that teachers in Surigao City, Philippines effectively implemented the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Filipino 10, focusing on the four core macro skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. This achievement reflects the adaptability and dedication of educators to maintain quality instruction despite the shift to distance learning modalities, whether modular or non-modular. In both types of instruction, a high percentage of competencies were taught, indicating that teachers prioritized these essential skills to ensure continuity of learning. Notably, modular instruction faced more challenges, as reflected by a slightly higher percentage of untaught competencies. This suggests that modular learning, which often relies on self-study and limited teacher interaction, posed additional obstacles for comprehensive skill coverage, particularly for competencies requiring guided practice like speaking and writing.

The successful implementation of MELCs across both public and private schools demonstrates a strong commitment from teachers to achieve educational goals amidst unprecedented challenges. Teachers' ability to adapt instructional strategies for both modular and non-modular modalities ensured that students could acquire essential knowledge and skills necessary for their progression to the next grade level. This consistency across learning modalities highlights the strength of the MELCs in providing focused, essential content. It also reflects the efforts of the Department of Education and local school administrations in supporting teachers' professional development and resource needs to navigate these challenges. The findings underscore the resilience of the educational system in Surigao City, Philippines. Teachers have the capacity to overcome limitations in resources and interaction to deliver meaningful learning experiences (Gaddi, 2024; Gesta et al., 2024).

Significant Correlation on the Implementation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in teaching Filipino 10 and the Profile Variables

Figure 3. Correlation Results between the Status of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) Implementation and Teachers' Profile Variables

Figure 3 shows that there is no significant correlation between the status of MELCs implementation and various teacher profile variables such as years of teaching experience, class size, teaching modality, or school type. This lack of correlation indicates that these variables did not have a notable influence on the overall implementation of the MELCs. Teachers were generally able to adapt to the requirements of the MELCs, regardless of the size of their class, their teaching experience, or whether they were teaching in public or private schools (Gaddi, 2024; Fajardo et al., 2024). This finding suggests a level of adaptability and resilience among Filipino teachers during the pandemic.

However, a significant relationship was identified between the implementation of MELCs in listening skills and the teachers' highest educational attainment. Teachers with higher levels of education were more effective in implementing listening-related competencies in Filipino 10. This finding underscores the importance of advanced education in equipping teachers with the necessary pedagogical skills and strategies to teach effectively, particularly in areas like listening, which can be more challenging in a distance learning context (Cabrigas et al., 2024; Gaddi, 2024). Listening skills are crucial for students' comprehension, especially when they are learning remotely and have limited face-to-face interaction with teachers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study sheds light on the overall successful implementation of DepEd's MELCs in Filipino 10 across Surigao City's secondary schools. Despite the challenges brought by the pandemic, the teachers adapted well to the new modalities, ensuring that students continued to develop essential skills. While variables such as teaching experience and class size did not significantly impact the implementation, teachers with higher educational qualifications were more adept at teaching specific competencies, particularly in listening.

Based on these findings, the study recommends continued professional development for teachers to enhance their ability to implement the MELCs, especially in areas that require more complex teaching strategies. Further research could explore the long-term impacts of modular and online learning on student outcomes and identify best practices for future educational disruptions. By doing so, the education sector can be better prepared for similar crises, ensuring that learning continues and essential competencies are developed, regardless of the circumstances.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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